

Deissinger, T., & Gonon, P. (2022). Continuity and change in dual apprenticeship systems: different historical pathways to 'hybridity' in vet in Germany and Switzerland. In C. Nägele, N. Kersh, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Trends in vocational education and training research, Vol. V. Proceedings of the European Conference on Educational Research (ECER), Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp. 34–36).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6975344>

Continuity and Change in Dual Apprenticeship Systems: Different Historical Pathways to 'Hybridity' in VET in Germany and Switzerland

Deissinger, Thomas

thomas.deissinger@uni-konstanz.de, University of Konstanz

Gonon, Philipp

gonon@ife.uzh.ch, University of Zurich, Switzerland

Abstract

Context: Dual apprenticeship systems receive major attention on account of their structural speciality, their traditional working, didactic and learning principles, and, above all, because they seem to solve the problem of integrating young people into the labour market relatively smoothly. In contrast to other VET systems the German and the Swiss VET system pay tribute to both private and public interests, including shared responsibilities. Furthermore, subsidiarity, not central regulation, plays a major role in what political science labels "collective skill formation" (Busemeyer & Trampusch, 2019).

Approach: This paper is based on a historical analysis of the development of the German and Swiss system. Furthermore, topical documents and research literature in both countries are evaluated and synthesized from a comparative perspective.

Findings: Although the German and Swiss VET system are labelled as dual apprenticeship countries differences in the development are important, which will shape the further pathways that aim at hybridity, including labour market access and possible changes in higher education.

Conclusion: Dual apprenticeships are still playing an important role in both countries. Each country-specific solution of adapting dual apprenticeships in a global economy and in the face of expanding higher education had to be elaborated based on collaborative governance and commonly shared issues.

Keywords: apprenticeship, dual system, hybridity

1 The development of the German and Swiss VET system

The importance and high reputation of VET in both countries today is based on institutional development, including legislative regulations. In the aftermath of the Second World War and especially in the 1960s this remarkable amount of stability, structural and conceptual conservatism has been challenged. In Germany and Switzerland in the turmoil of the late 1960s and early 1970s (Greinert, 1994), pushing for educational reforms and the overcoming of established patterns, such as the three-tier secondary school system, the apprenticeship system also was at stake. Furthermore, the boost of baccalaureate schools led to a rising pressure to reform and modernize dual apprenticeships but did not lead to giving up the vocational principle in VET, the subsidiarity principle and consensus building - parameters mostly recurring to the late 19th century (Deissinger & Gonon, 2021).

Germany and Switzerland share the commonality of a VET system which gives apprenticeships, though to a varying degree, a crucial weight and relevance within the post-secondary

education system. Nevertheless, there are nation-specific differences even between Germany and Switzerland, which we will highlight in this paper. We treat Germany and Switzerland as two cases which are not juxtapositional but similar at least in their historical situation impacting vocational education at the beginning of the 20th century. In the course of history, however, due to various often dramatical political and economic developments, VET and dual apprenticeships followed different pathways in the two countries that are still visible today.

The obvious stability of the apprenticeship system seems to be one of the reasons why links between higher and vocational education, including hybridity, i.e. the formal combination of a vocational and a general qualification, are rather weak in Germany (Deissinger et al, 2013). Differently, in Switzerland, the establishment of the professional baccalaureate has led to a hybrid system (Gonon 2013), which does not set the VET sector apart and offers access to tertiary education.

Young people not going to university in Germany and Switzerland traditionally undertake apprenticeships in the dual system (Greinert 1994; Deissinger 2010; Wettstein et al. 2017). The dual system is a major pathway into skilled employment and also a crucial element of workforce development for many companies. As an apprenticeship system, its core aim is to qualify young people for carrying out an "occupation". However today, more and more young people tend to start immediately (in a baccalaureate school) or later (due to new programs leading to a bachelor degree) with an academically oriented learning pathway.

2 Differences regarding the current features and the importance of apprenticeships in both countries

When comparing Germany and Switzerland today, we can discern a number of similar but also different features regarding dual apprenticeships. In both countries, occupations play a decisive role in training young people for the world of work. Both countries still rely on a strong dual system and try to strengthen and stabilise this model also for the future. A pivotal element is the engagement of employers who are needed to guarantee that the systems still remain attractive for young people. Until now, in both countries (though to a larger degree in Switzerland), they are committed to training and do not want to delegate this task to schools or the state (Deissinger and Gonon 2016).

Having stressed the commonalities, we can look at different recent developments in both countries. The pathway to higher education and the importance of courses involving companies within the higher education system regarding the aspect of duality are different. Dualisation within higher education and, at the same time, with it a specific kind of "vocalisation", have now become familiar features of an increasingly differentiated higher education system in Germany – e.g. with the *Berufsakademien* in the state of Baden-Württemberg (vocational academies which combine academic and practical training) now called "dual universities" (Deissinger 2010).

In Switzerland, the Federal Vocational Baccalaureate, introduced in 1993, has been the most important innovation in the last decades. It enables the transition from the - until then - quite isolated system of VET into the field of academic education and has gained recognition from the majority of stakeholders in educational policy and the public. In particular, it has become accepted by young people and their parents as a course of education which offers continuative options and therefore functions as an alternative to the traditional grammar school-based academic track (Wettstein et al. 2017).

3 Conclusion

In identifying the challenges for dual systems in Germany and Switzerland, we have focused on hybridity. Hybridity can be identified as an element of reframing (in Switzerland) or

transferring the apprenticeship model (in Germany) not just towards the world of work but also to the education system, thus opening further career paths for young people.

References

- Busemeyer, M.R., & Trampusch, C. (2019). The politics of vocational training: Theories, typologies, and public policies. In D. Guile & L. Unwin (Eds.), *The Wiley handbook of vocational education and training* (pp. 137-164). Wiley Blackwell.
- Deissinger, T. (2010). Dual System. in: P. Peterson, E. Baker & B. McGaw (Eds.), *International Encyclopedia of Education*, (3rd Edition, Vol. 8 pp.448-454), Elsevier.
- Deissinger, T., Aff, J., Fuller, A., & Helms Jorgensen, C. (Eds.) (2013). *Hybrid Qualifications: structures and problems in the context of European VET policy*, Peter Lang.
- Deissinger, T., & Gonon, P. (2016). Stakeholders in the German and Swiss VET system and their role in innovating apprenticeships against the background of academisation. *Education and Training*, 58 (6), 1-11.
- Deissinger, T., & Gonon, P. (2021). The development and cultural foundations of dual apprenticeships – a comparison of Germany and Switzerland, in: *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 73 (2), 197-216.
- Gonon, Ph. (2013). Federal Vocational Baccalaureate: The Swiss way of „hybridity“. In T. Deissinger, J. Aff, A. Fuller & C. Helms Jörgensen (Eds.), *Hybrid Qualifications – Structures and Problems in the Context of European VET Policy* (pp. 181-196). Peter Lang
- Gonon, P. (2017). Quality doubts as a driver for vocational education and training (VET) reforms – Switzerland’s way to a highly regarded apprenticeship system. In M. Pilz (Ed.): *Vocational education and training in times of economic crisis* (pp. 341-354). Springer
- Greinert, W.-D. (1994). *The "German System" of vocational training. History, organization, prospects*. nomos
- Wettstein, E., Schmid, E., & Gonon, P. (2017). *Swiss vocational and Professional Education and Training (VPET). Forms, system, stakeholders*. hep

Biographical notes

Dr **Thomas Deissinger** is a professor at the University in Konstanz, Germany. His research includes international comparative perspectives on the VET systems of Australia, England, and Canada in particular, but also looks at other European countries.

Dr **Philipp Gonon** is a professor em. at the University of Zürich, where he researches and teaches vocational pedagogy, history and theory of (vocational) education, quality assurance, program evaluation, as well as issues on international comparison in education.